

Uncovering Users of Anonymization Networks Using Traditional
Investigative Techniques

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Abstract

Anonymization networks such as Tor provide anonymity indiscriminately to anybody who installs the applicable, easy to use, ready out of the box, software. From a technical point of view, these networks are generally well designed and reasonably secure. During the course of an investigation, if a law enforcement agent comes into contact with such a network, they often look at the problem head on and become overwhelmed with the complexity and sophistication of the network. The solution to the problem of uncovering users of anonymization networks does not lie with taking the network head on; but instead it should be understood that even the most technically adept person is still just a person, and they will make operational security mistakes. Those mistakes are the metaphorical chinks in the armor of anonymization networks. In this paper, we will examine past cases where users of anonymization networks were uncovered using investigative tactics that have been around for centuries; we will look at how they were uncovered, and how those cases can be generalized to nearly any case involving users of anonymization networks. We will also examine mistakes on the part of investigators that tainted evidence so that it was unusable, legally or technically, and how to avoid such contaminations and mistakes. We will focus on the Tor network as it is the most widely used, but these ideas and principles can be applied to nearly any anonymization network.

Keywords: Tor, Networks, Anonymization, Law Enforcement, Investigation

Special Consideration Surrounding Conflict of Interest

Before diving into how to investigate users hidden behind anonymization, it is important to touch on a malicious conflict of interest that may exist in investigative teams due to the pervasive influence of and well-hidden user affiliation with hidden services, as well as the ease of hiding changes to digital evidence. Due to the nature of services and users hidden via anonymization networks, it is important to be extremely careful in the collection, storage, and dissemination of evidence. A lot of evidence such as money and data can be tampered with or stolen over the course of an investigation; because of the nature of non-physical items such as Bitcoin, it is often easy to miss these malicious actions. Take for example, the case of the two Silk Road taskforce investigators, DEA agent Carl Mark Force IV and Secret Service agent Shaun Bridges. During the course of the investigation into the Silk Road these two agents both “had significant exposure to and developed expertise in the digital currency known as Bitcoin” (Dalton, 2017). Using this expertise, these two men stole Bitcoins from Silk Road using information and access gained through the taskforce. A basic summary of how they did it goes as such; Bridges and Force gained access to a Silk Road administrative account after a Silk Road employee was arrested. Using that account, the two agents transferred a large sum of Bitcoins to an account with a company called Mt. Gox; which owned and operated a Bitcoin currency exchange platform under the same name. The two agents then converted the Bitcoin into United States Dollars, and used it to fund a Fidelity investment account under the name “Quantum International Investments LLC.”, a company founded and owned by Agent Bridges (Dalton). The intent was clearly to make a profit using money that was unofficially seized during the course and as a result of the investigation. The two were caught when multiple items raised red flags. First, agent Force attempted to have his personal account on the Venmo money platform unfrozen, as it “had

previously been frozen due to certain suspicious activity” (Dalton). Force then attempted to cover this up by requesting Venmo not contact the DEA, a request which they did not follow (DEA, 5). Once Venmo declined to follow their request, Force and Bridges attempted to recruit an IRS agent to illegally freeze Venmo’s bank accounts (Dalton) in order to force compliance. This chain of events led to the taskforce’s leaders and parent agencies becoming aware of Force’s and Bridge’s activities. From this, it can be learned that just because a person is a law enforcement agent does not mean that they will follow the law. It is important to ensure that agents continue to follow proper procedures, and any indiscretions, no matter how minor, should be brought to the attention of those superior to the offender. It is also important to remember that agents may also be working with the leadership of offending services, and so information should be compartmentalized as to prevent rogue agents from gathering information easily. It should also be noted that the malicious activities of the agents in this case were uncovered because they were reported by multiple concerned individuals; vigilance in this case was more valuable than extensive technical means; this is a theme in many cases surrounding anonymization networks.

Discovery of Obfuscated Networked Services

All services offered via anonymization networks, whether it be an illegal black market, child pornography site, terrorist message board, or something else, are in essence standard networked services like Facebook or Reddit, but they are masked behind several network hops, and they may have software which is hardened to avoid leaking data regarding the architecture of such services; such as where the servers are located, and the architecture of the servers being used. Normally, security experts need to think like a defender, they can never be wrong; in this case however they can act as attackers, meaning the operator of the service only has to be wrong once for a lead to develop. A prime example of operational security mistakes made by a service

operator is that of the Silk Road black market. Silk Road was a service that acted in a similar fashion to EBay, but specialized in illegal items such as drugs, fake IDs, and counterfeit currency. The downfall of the Silk Road started when it was discovered that “The Internet protocol (“IP”) address of the [Silk Road] Server (the “Subject IP Address”) was “leaking” from the site due to an apparent misconfiguration of the user login interface by the site administrator” (United States of America v. Ross Ulbricht, 2014). Through careful examination of the site, this vulnerability was uncovered. Many believed that the NSA was involved in a highly elaborate operation to catch the operator of the Silk Road, but in reality, the servers were found due to a simple misconfiguration in the software running the site which caused non-Tor IP address to be included in the header of requests to the website (United States of America v. Ross Ulbricht). Once investigators had the address of one server, they were able to quickly enumerate the other servers involved as they were then able to seize information stored on the original server; of particular interest was “the IP address of a server used to back up the contents of the [Silk Road] Server, housed at a data center in Pennsylvania” (United States of America v. Ross Ulbricht). This discovery brought law enforcement one step closer to a man named Ross Ulbricht, who had gone to school in Pennsylvania and quickly became the primary suspect. Law enforcement was then able to use a pen register to track when Ross Ulbricht was on the Internet. The information gained from the pen register was then used to correlate the times Ulbricht was on the Internet to times when the Silk Road administrator was online (United States of America v. Ross Ulbricht). This method can be thought of as a type of correlation attack, and it is one of the most powerful tools an investigator has when working around anonymization networks. Correlation attacks can also be used to discover things like where sites are hosted. For example, by examining the downtime of a service, and comparing it to the downtime of suspected hosting providers which

are often publically posted, and the downtime of other sites, an investigator can find with a pretty good probability of being correct, the hosting provider of a hidden service. There are some cases where correlation attacks are not effective. If a target uses an anonymization network sparingly, there will not be a lot of data to use in correlation, and so another method will have to be used.

Discovery of Service Users

While seizing services generally brings down large groups at once, generally these groups are able to come back together if only the services are taken down while the majority of users are left intact. Take for example the case of the Silk Road which was just examined; after the service shut down several similar services took its place. Targeting users of these illegal services serves two-fold; for one it acts as a sort of psychological deterrent against future users of the targeted service and similar services, and it also has the standard impact of removing criminals from society. Generally targeting users comes after targeting a service, but it can be done without bringing a service down as well.

One case to look at when considering discovery of users is the Freedom Hosting case. Freedom hosting is a now defunct hosting platform, that offered hosting on Tor based websites, and it is estimated to have been the largest single distributor of child pornography. One of the things that separates this case from others, and makes it truly unique is the fact the FBI actually hosted the site for a brief time so that it could act as a honeypot of sorts. When targeting users it is important to remember that just because a user accesses a site does not mean that the user is a criminal. In the case of the Freedom Hosting child porn investigation there were multiple checks to confirm that users were actually using the sites to access and distribute the illegal materials. First, users connecting to the site “might obtain the web address directly from communicating with other users of the board, or from Internet postings describing the sort of content is available

on one of the website as well as the website's location” (An Affidavit in Support of Application for Search Warrant, 2016); this means that users visiting the site were unlikely to simply stumble upon it, some thought was probably put into obtaining the service address. Second, some sites such as the site presented only as “Website 1” required that users upload original child pornography before they were granted an account on the site (An Affidavit in Support), many sites also required that users remain active. Lastly, users were only flagged for investigation if they downloaded content. All of this combined removes any reasonable suspicion regarding the users of these sites.

The same technical bugs, and operational security failures presented earlier can be used to attack users. While the actual technique used in catching users in the Freedom Hosting case remains classified, many individual parts of the attack are well known and understood. The main component involves building a digital fingerprint of users – which is sometimes incredibly easy. The Tor Browser Bundle is the software that is generally used to access the Tor network; and with only a few exceptions, most users are running the same setup as Tor strongly discourages changing settings within the browser or using a different browser entirely. This is of huge benefit because if an exploit is found with one user, it will generally work with most users. In this case, there were some leaks of information gathered via JavaScript and general browser exploitation; the information gathered was as follows: The user’s true IP, operating system, computer architecture information, hostname, and MAC address (An Affidavit in Support). All of these items are used to uniquely identify a computer; in this case, the IP address was used to track down a user’s location, and the rest of the fingerprint was used to identify the specific device used at that location to access the illegal service. In all cases it is necessary to conduct a follow-up investigation with this information, as simply knowing the computer was used is likely not

enough to bring a suspect to court. This was made clear in the piracy court case *Cobbler Nevada LLC. V. Thomas Gonzales*, which was dismissed with the statement “While it is possible that the subscriber is also the person who downloaded the movie, it is also possible that a family member, a resident of the household, or an unknown person engage in the infringing conduct” (*Cobbler Nevada LLC. v. Thomas Gonzales*, 2016). To put the Gonzales case into simpler terms, and IP address is a number used to identify a network node, which has multiple users. Given only a single IP address, it is still not possible to identify a single user with an acceptable level of certainty; this is why information about a user’s specific device such as the MAC address is invaluable, that can identify a specific user on a network. The investigation needs to confirm, without a reasonable doubt that the user was in control of their computer and nobody else had access at the time of the download. Special care needs to be taken to ensure that the computer had no remote administration tools installed. There have been cases such as the United Kingdom Cafferty hacking case where a jury found a defendant not guilty because the prosecution could not prove that only the suspect had access and control over their system when crimes occurred. Specifically, in the Cafferty case, the jury came to the conclusion that a “Trojan horse armed with a 'wiping tool' was responsible, enabling the computer to launch the DoS attack, edit the system's log files, and then delete all traces of the Trojan” (Brenner, Carrier, Henninger, 2004) A forensic review of a suspect’s hard drive, along with evidence that they were at the workstation at the time of the incident should be sufficient to ensure confirmation of guilt.

A final example of a Tor user being uncovered is the case of Eldo Kim, a student at Harvard who was caught sending a bomb threat despite using Tor to cover his tracks. In an affidavit attached to the case *United States of America v. Eldo Kim*, it was revealed that the police were able to uncover Kim’s identity because “in the several hours leading up to the receipt of the e-mail

messages described above, ELDO KIM accessed TOR using Harvard's wireless network." (Dalton, 2013). In this case, a bomb threat was sent via "Guerrilla Mail [...] using a product called TOR" (Dalton); because Kim was the only person the connect to Tor via the Harvard network during a feasible time leading up to the threat being sent, he was made the primary suspect, and quickly confessed. The confession in this case was invaluable, as just knowing that Kim was connected to Tor was not enough to prove that he was the source of the threat. A confession in this case was used in addition to a sort of correlation attack; the correlation attack identified a suspect, and a confession confirmed his guilt.

Ensuring Evidence Remains Technically Feasible

There are many countermeasures which criminals may use to destroy, or obfuscate evidence so that it is not usable in court. The main countermeasure employed is often file or full disk encryption. It is extremely important that a suspect not be allowed to handle their computer at all after becoming aware of a police action against them. Encryption is considered viable generally only when a computer is powered down; meaning keys for encrypted data can easily be gathered from RAM if the system is powered on and a hardware security module is not in use. There are several cases which show the effectiveness of gathering keys from computers which are still turned on, namely the investigation into Albert Gonzales, one of the hackers involved in the famous TJX hacking case; "pre-raid preparations and on-scene search strategies were crafted to maximize the opportunity to gain access to running systems and the data they contained." (Casey, Fellows, Geiger, Stellatos, 2004). As a result of careful planning and execution, data on Gonzales' computers was successfully obtained and used against him in court. There are also cases where data could not be gathered due to a system being powered down during a raid. An example of this occurring is the case of Sebastien Boucher; he was observed possessing child

pornography on his computer while crossing the Canadian-American border; however, “his computer was turned off before a forensic duplicate was acquired, and all of the alleged child pornography was inaccessible apparently because it was locked in an encrypted volume” (Casey, Fellows, Geiger, Stellatos). In addition to ensuring data is captured in an accessible manner, it is also important that multiple backups be taken; one advantage law enforcement officials have with digital evidence is the ease of duplication.

Ensuring Evidence Remains Legally Feasible

It is important to remember that investigations into digital services are very similar to physical investigations in terms of evidence collection. Servers and other computer equipment should be treated as physical property. Breaking into a server without a warrant or using an invalid warrant will be tolerated just as breaking into a home without probable cause or a valid warrant would be in court, meaning not at all. During and FBI operation, codenamed “Operation Playpen”, multiple users of child pornography sites were caught via FBI sanctioned malware attacks. The court ruled that the warrant allowing for data collection was invalid with the following statement.

If the “installation” occurred on the government-controlled computer, located in the Eastern District of Virginia, applying the tracking device exception breaks down, because [the out-of-state defendant] never controlled the government-controlled computer, unlike a car with a tracking device leaving a particular district. If the installation occurred on [the out-of-state defendant’s] computer, applying the tracking device exception again fails, because [the out-of-state defendant’s] computer was never physically located within the Eastern District of Virginia. (United States of America v. Beau Brandon Croghan, 2016)

Essentially, the evidence was inadmissible because a judge in one district cannot issue a warrant for another district. It is important to remember that while borders and jurisdictions are difficult to judge on cases involving computer networks, they are still important to make note of, and generally a warrant is needed in every district in which evidence is collected. Jurisdiction is a complicated piece of digital investigations. To make use of the fact that passing data through multiple jurisdictions makes it hard for law enforcement to track a suspect. Police in Riga, Latvia are unlikely to work with police in Sioux Falls, Iowa, especially if the crime being tracked is something relatively minor such as a bomb threat. At the end of the day a case may go cold because a node on the Tor network does not have logs, or data travels outside of an investigator's jurisdiction.

Non-Traditional Investigative Techniques

There are several non-traditional tactics which are being developed, and/or are in use currently to track hidden services, and users. One of the most interesting developments in this field is the tool codenamed "EGOTISTICALGIRAFFE", an NSA tool used to exploit parts of Tor to track down users. It has been touted that this tool has "succeeded in unmasking 24 Tor users in a single weekend" (NSA slideshow). The way EGOTISTICALGIRAFFE works is mostly classified, but leaks by Edward Snowden show that it exploits multiple problems with both the design of the Tor web browser, and add-ons to that browser. First, it can identify Tor users because something called the a BuildID, which is a part of FireFox which is available for web servers to see, is set to 0 only on the Tor browser (NSA slideshow). The program can then run exploits using JavaScript, which is allowed by default in Tor, and other browser specific exploits to gain information from a user's computer to uniquely identify that user (NSA slideshow). This

exploit, along with others, is just part of the ever-growing pool of research into how to identify and track Tor users. If law enforcement has access to such tools, they should use them sparingly, as to not attract attention to there being a vulnerability in Tor. Shortly after the Snowden leaks which included information about EGOTISTICALGIRAFFE, the exploits used in that specific operation were mostly patched by Tor. Anonymization networks are becoming part of a modern arms race, with one side seeking to exploit these networks, and another side trying to protect them. Battles in this race are being won and lost on both sides; only time will tell who will win the war.

Conclusion

Law enforcement officers have some advantages when conducting investigations around anonymization networks. Officers often have a large amount of time to study their targets and formulate plans. If investigations are done correctly, technology can yield rich information trails. There are some places where officers have disadvantages as well. If a target is only available on the network for a short time, and they are skilled in counterintelligence, they can often evade law enforcement for a longer time than in a standard case. An investigator should work using the advantages they have. Tor is neither good or bad; there are many cases where the Tor network has been used to save the lives of individuals in dangerous situations, and aid law enforcement in undercover investigations. Tor and other anonymization networks are just another piece of an ever-growing technical toolset available to everyone. It is impossible and counterproductive to remove this technology, and so governments and law enforcement agents should study cases that have occurred around anonymization networks, learn from those cases, and adapt for the future.

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